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MODERN APPROACHES TO MAKING STUDENTS INTERESTED IN THE PROFESSION

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the initial pedagogical processes in guiding students to the profession, and in this process, the teacher's pedagogical skills, knowledge and skills related to choosing a profession, tasks, as well as personality traits in choosing a profession, student psychology, information is given about the content of the criteria that indicate the readiness of students to choose a profession.

The strategic direction of the development of the education system in society is the intellectual and moral development of a person based on his purposeful independent activity in various fields. Along with the developed countries of the world, the promotion of independent education is an important direction in the process of educational reforms in our country.

The research of the phenomenon of educating the professional competence of the pedagogue has been expressed in the works of a number of scientists. These authors put forward the opinion that together with the qualities of professional competence and reliability, they describe the pedagogical culture of the teacher as a professional and individual phenomenon. In turn, the concept of professional competence, as stated by V.A. Slastenin, represents the unity of the theoretical and practical readiness of the pedagogue to carry out pedagogical activities and describes his professional formation. In the conditions of the market economy, the importance of choosing the right profession in people's well-being and activities, the requirements of various professions; world of professions, family tree of professions, important professions in the national economy of Uzbekistan, classifier of professions; training system of junior specialists; professions, working conditions, tools, science, purpose, students' interests and inclinations, the unique features of their character, their nervous structure, psyche, their abilities and needs. to obtain information about the schools, the changing needs of certain professions based on the labor market requirements, the suitability of their health to the chosen profession, the voluntary choice of the direction of education in secondary special, vocational educational institutions located in the region; opportunities to continue studying. He needs to know his future position.

Choosing the right profession is an important step in a person's life, success in the whole life of the young generation largely depends on how correctly the profession is chosen. In order to make the right choice of profession according to the interests, inclinations, abilities

and possibilities of each school student, it is necessary to take into account his health, mastery and emotions, these are the most important in socially useful and productive work. It becomes more determined and manifested.

If a person has a creative attitude to the work he does, constantly increases his labor productivity, looks at his chosen profession with great interest, understands the social importance of his work, if his abilities improve at work, then only then will he be satisfied with work and be happy. This kind of care brings the most benefits to society for each individual. The extremely important social importance of choosing a profession comes from these words. Free choice of profession is very important. If a person likes the work he is doing, he will be happy, satisfied, take great initiative, tirelessly increase his productivity. The choice of a profession by schoolchildren should be a conscious necessity and at the same time should be in line with the interests of the society and meet the personal needs of young men and women on the way to maturity. For this, it is necessary to be educated at a high level, in our present age, science and technology cannot progress without such education. Such opportunities to form general and special skills, interests in the profession have an objective basis, and in reality are being increased every day. It is a system of scientifically based forms, methods and means of influencing a person to find his professional position. It is aimed at achieving a balance between a person's professional interests and capabilities and the needs of society for a specific type of professional activity.

Vocational orientation is a socio-economic category according to the essence and efficiency evaluation indicators. Vocational orientation is a problem of socio-economic, medical-physiological and psychological-pedagogical essence. Vocational orientation allows for the purposeful development of a person's abilities and talents, the preservation of his professional skills, work ability and health, and is manifested as one of the important elements of the state policy in the field of social protection of the population and its employment. Vocational guidance plays an important role in effective use of a person's labor potential, increasing his social and professional activity, and preventing forced unemployment. Vocational guidance activities help people to search for convenient ways to improve their professional skills, develop socio-economic initiative, intellectual and labor independence. Preparing the young generation to consciously choose a profession is considered as a condition for its comprehensive and comprehensive development. It is carried out in harmony with the spiritual, mental, labor, aesthetic and physical education of a person, that is, with the entire educational process. Vocational guidance includes the following parts: Vocational information, vocational counseling, vocational selection and selection, vocational adjustment. Vocational information - requirements for a person who wants to acquire a certain profession, the forms and conditions of acquiring various specialties, opportunities for the growth of professional skills, the state and needs of the labor market, the formation of professional interests, the wishes and skills of a person, and modern collection of information on the prospects and content of professions, promotion measures.

Vocational counseling - the study of the individual psychological characteristics, personal qualities, professional interests, inclinations, health, and labor market needs of a person who needs help in choosing a profession or changing the content of activities is

basically a scientifically organized interaction with a psychological counselor. consists of a communication system.

Vocational selection and selection is a system of comprehensive study of a person on the basis of psychophysiological characteristics of a person (selection) or psychophysiological normative requirements for a specific profession (selection), aimed at determining the level of suitability for certain types of professional activity.

Professional adaptation is a complex system of measures aimed at adapting a person to the socio-psychological and organizational-technical conditions of professional activity in production, creating conditions for him to successfully occupy the profession.

Professionography (information, diagnosis, corrective, formative) and professional diagnosis (a set of psychological, psychophysiological, medical and other methods of studying a person) are the basis of the information-methodical sequence of career guidance. Students can analyze professions; it is necessary to be able to correctly evaluate their personal qualities, interests and health levels, to be able to compare their individual characteristics with the requirements of professions, and to make personal professional plans. Students will learn about the national economy sectors, the reforms taking place in the national economy, the requirements of the market economy, state-private enterprises, cooperatives, firms, companies, concerns, and the organization of production in them according to the section on the basics of national economy. forms of production, technological processes, stages of product preparation, protection of nature from the harmful effects of production, ways to reduce the cost of products, periodicity, regularity, flow of production in agriculture; production planning, irrigation and reclamation works; must know labor legislation.

The main stages of development of career guidance. The main stages of development of vocational guidance are as follows:

The first stage (pre-school age) - children of pre-school age (large group) who will be busy with work, their classes, as well as the types of activities that they can do, will positively acquire their initial professional skills. , emotional-affective formation;

The second stage (grades 1-4) - through the implementation of cognitive and socially useful labor activities in the form of games, respect for labor, understanding of its place in human life and society, parents development of interest in their mothers' professions and public professions;

The third stage (grades 5-7) is the formation of searching and careful manifestations of the interests, abilities, and social values of teenagers related to choosing a profession and finding their place in society;

The fourth stage (grades 8-9) is the period of formation of students' professional self-awareness, i.e. students understand the personal meaning of choosing a specific profession, their ideas about values , the period of forming the ability to compare the choice of the field of activity with the goals of the society;

The fifth stage (first-year students of academic lyceums and vocational colleges) - determination of social and professional status, that is, formation of comprehensive ideas about knowledge and skills in a specific field of work, starting to master them, production the period of forming adherence to the procedures and values of the labor team;

The sixth stage (students of the last year of vocational colleges, students of higher educational institutions) - starting professional activity. This is the period of serious preparation for professional activity and the formation of work and experience in the labor team; Seventh stage (elderly employed people, unemployed) - reorientation to other professional activities if necessary, taking into account personal capabilities and previous professional and social experiences.

In addition to the state career guidance system, bureaus and agencies can be established that can provide paid services to citizens and enterprises on career guidance issues, including commercial ones. Vocational orientation of persons with limited working capacity is entrusted to the ministries of labor and social protection of the population, health. At all management levels of the system, these ministries allocate responsible personnel for this work.

It is necessary to create a network of specialized departments for professional training of disabled people with various pathologies in higher and secondary special and vocational educational institutions. General scientific-methodological support of career guidance, retraining and upgrading of relevant categories of employees, coordination of scientific investigations on socio-economic, psychological-pedagogical and medical-physiological problems are carried out by the People's Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is carried out by the Psychological and Pedagogical Republican Diagnostic Center of the Ministry of Education. If children do not learn to think freely, it is inevitable that the effectiveness of the given education will be low. Of course, knowledge is needed. But knowledge is on its way. Independent thinking is also a great asset. While talking about the weak sides of comprehensive schools, we cannot pass without highlighting one important problem. This problem is the fate of our children graduating from the 9th grade today.

Out of approximately 5 million 200 thousand schoolchildren in our republic, 450 thousand children are graduating from the 9th grade. Well, let's imagine what the next path - fate of those who finish the 9th grade will be? According to the data, about 250,000 of them, i.e. 55%, continue their studies in the 10th grade, and about 100,000 can enter vocational - technical or special educational institutions. And the rest - we are talking about 100,000 of our children - according to the calculation, remain on the streets. This information is also incomplete. 20,000-25,000 of those graduating from the 11th grade, that is, 10% of all, can enter higher educational institutions. The remaining 90 percent cannot acquire a specific specialty, a qualification necessary for tomorrow's life, or a profession. And as a result, our 16-18-year-old boys and girls are unable to find a place in life that matches their abilities, passion, and aspirations. I don't believe that anyone who deeply analyzes these numbers and this sad situation, takes it from his heart and understands it as his personal pain, will be indifferent to such a situation. That is why today's demand and the concerns of our future require us to reform the public education system.

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